

Results and Discussion

Some important results are shown in Table 1. Ceric salt alone can initiate the polymerization of MMA, but the presence of benzoic acid considerably increased R_p , being proportional to the acid concentration. There was a slight reduction in $\bar{P}_n$ with increasing benzoic acid concentration. With increasing ceric ion concentration R_p remained practically unaffected, but there was a sharp fall in $\bar{P}_n$. Both R_p and $\bar{P}_n$ decreased with decreasing MMA concentration.

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF AQUEOUS POLYMERIZATION OF MMA WITH CERIC-BENZOIC ACID SYSTEM*

[Ce ⁴⁺] M × 10 ³	[Benzoic acid] M × 10 ³	[MMA] M	R _p mol l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ × 10 ⁶	$\bar{P}_n$
1.27	Nil	0.094	0.0487	4631
1.27	4.59	0.094	4.74	3816
1.27	3.06	0.094	3.18	4065
1.27	1.53	0.094	1.80	4329
3.81	1.53	0.094	1.77	2536
12.70	1.53	0.094	1.82	1083
1.27	1.53	0.047	0.83	2734
1.27	1.53	0.019	0.36	1652

* [H₂SO₄] = 10⁻³ M and Temp. 30°.

Graphical plotting of these data shows that R_p is approximately proportional to the monomer as well as the benzoic acid concentration, but independent of ceric ion concentration.

Palit's dye test⁶ demonstrated the presence of hydroxyl endgroups⁷ in all the polymer samples, but carboxyl endgroups⁸ were absent.

These results suggest that the ceric ions participate in both initiation and termination reactions and that the initiating radicals contain only hydroxyl groups and no carboxyl groups. On the basis of our preliminary findings and the knowledge of the reported⁹ reaction of benzoic acid and ceric ions, the following mechanism of initiation is tentatively suggested.

where M represents the monomer.

That the hydroxyl endgroups in the polymer is not due to oxidation of water by ceric ions, was

proved by the fact that the polymer samples prepared in dimethyl sulphoxide medium also showed the presence of hydroxyl endgroups. Further work is in progress.

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Extractive Photometric Determination of Iron(III) with N-Hydroxy-N, N'-diarylbenzamidines from Thiocyanate Solutions

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N-Hydroxy-N, N'-diarylbenzamidines, newly synthesised organic reagents having monobasic and bidentate functional grouping¹⁻⁴ reacts with iron(III) in thiocyanate medium giving water insoluble red-orange mixed-complexes. The mixed-complexes are extractable into benzene with ϵ , 1.0-1.2 × 10⁴ l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 460-465 nm. Iron(III)-thiocyanate method⁵ is commonly used for determination of iron(III), but this method suffer with a number of analytical factors such as time of standing, thiocyanate concentration, non-linearity of Beer's law, etc. However, these factors are overcome in proposed mixed thiocyanato method. The selectivity and sensitivity of iron(III)-N-hydroxyamidine-thiocyanate method may be compared to other established methods⁶. The present paper reports the extractive-photometric determination of microgram quantities of iron(III) as thiocyanato mixed-complexes with seven newly synthesised N-hydroxyamidines. The method is applicable to determine iron in ores,

alloys, etc.

(where R_1 = phenyl/*p*-chlorophenyl/*p*-tolyl/*o*-tolyl ;
 R_2 = phenyl/(2-methyl-4-chloro)phenyl/
 α -naphthylamine ;
 R_3 = phenyl)

Experimental

Apparatus : An ECIL UV-VIS spectrophotometer model-865 matched with 1 cm quartz and silica cells and a Systronic pH meter type-322 were used for measuring absorbance and pH values respectively.

Reagents and Chemicals : All the chemicals and reagents used were of BDH AnalaR grade. The stock solution of iron(III) was prepared by dissolving iron wire (E. Merck) in 30% nitric acid. The oxides of nitrogen were removed by boiling and solution was standardised gravimetrically⁶.

N-Hydroxy-N, N'-diarylbenzamidines were synthesised by condensation of equimolar ratio of N-arylbenzimidoyl chloride and corresponding N-arylhydroxylamine in ether medium^{1,7}. Hydrochlorides were crystallised from absolute ethanol while free bases from benzene : petroleum ether (2 : 1).

Purified benzene was used for preparation of reagents (0.1% w/v) and experimental works.

Procedure : An aliquot of iron(III) solution containing 50 μ g of metal was taken in a 150 ml separatory funnel. A 5 ml thiocyanate solution (2% w/v) was added with subsequent adjusting the acidity to 0.4 M HCl in final dilution of 25 ml. The iron(III) content was extracted with 25 ml benzene solution of reagent for 1 min. Transfer the benzene layer to 50 ml beaker containing 2 g anhydrous sodium sulphate. The absorbance values were measured at λ_{max} against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

All the reagents show negligible absorption at 450-700 nm. The thiocyanate mixed-chelates show the wavelength of maximum absorption at 460-465 nm with molar absorptivities in the range between $1.0-1.2 \times 10^4$ l mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The systems obey Beer's law up to 4.6 ppm of iron(III). Ringbom plot⁸ suggest optimum and effective metal concentration range of 0.8-3.8 ppm. The Sandell's sensitivity of the colour reactions are found to be 0.0046-0.0055 μ g per cm². The precision of the method evaluated by taking 10 measurements, lie between $\pm 0.56-0.82\%$ (each containing 2 ppm of Fe(III)/25 ml).

Effect of Variables : The various solvents like benzene, toluene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride,

etc., extract the thiocyanato mixed chelates with same λ_{max} but different absorbance values. The benzene is found to be the best solvent as mixed chelates and reagents show high distribution ratio in it. The acidity of aqueous phase is maintained with hydrochloric acid. Other acids are unsuitable for acidity adjustment because of low absorbance of the colour system. The optimum acidity ranges lie between 0.2-0.8M HCl. Below 0.2M HCl the position of absorption band is intact but absorption value is affected. As the acidity of aqueous phase is increased (0.2-0.8 M) the rate of extraction is decreased, so 0.4 M HCl is selected for further experimental works.

About 25 fold molar excess of reagent in the presence of excess thiocyanate at 0.4M HCl is adequate for complete extraction of iron(III). Similarly 120 fold molar excess of thiocyanate in the presence of 0.1% w/v reagent in benzene is necessary for complete extraction of iron(III). Addition of more reagents (N-hydroxyamidine up to 100 and thiocyanate up to 5000 fold molar excess) cause no adverse effect in the determination of iron(III). Order of addition of reagent is not critical. The usual way of addition is iron(III), acid, thiocyanate and reagent. A equilibrium time of 1 min is sufficient for full colour development. The benzene extracts are stable for at least 30 hrs at $27 \pm 2^\circ$. Variation in temperature from 20 to 35° and volume of aqueous phase from 15 to 60 ml do not affect the λ_{max} and absorbance of coloured system. No effect of ionic strength (up to 3 M NaCl/KCl) is noted as the ternary complexes show high distribution ratio in benzene.

Composition : In iron(III)-thiocyanato mixed-chelates the ratio of iron(III) to reagent and thiocyanate were determined by curve fitting method⁹ (log absorbance vs log M of reagent/SCN⁻). The results obtained show the formation of 1 : 2 : 1 (metal : thiocyanate : reagent) mixed chelates.

Effect of Diverse Ions : In the determination of 2 ppm of iron(III) the effect of diverse ions were studied as described in earlier procedure. Chloride, bromide, nitrate, sulphate, phthalate, borate, alkali and alkaline earth-elements and lanthanoid elements did not interfere up to 2000 ppm. The tolerance limits of other ions causing an error less than 2% are given in parenthesis (in ppm) : Ti⁴⁺(60) ; Zr⁴⁺(80) ; Mn²⁺(400) ; Cr³⁺(500) ; Tl³⁺(1200) ; Th⁴⁺(1200) ; W⁶⁺(40) ; Mo⁶⁺(80) ; V⁵⁺(20) ; Ni²⁺, Co²⁺(1200) ; Hg²⁺, Cd²⁺(1200) ; Al³⁺, Zn²⁺(1200) ; Be²⁺(1600) ; Cu²⁺(100) ; Ag⁺(800) ; Bi³⁺(1600) ; fluoride(600).

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